

THE IMPORTANCE OF SAVING ECOLOGY FOR ECOTOURISM

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ABSTARCT

Additionally, ecotourism is a part of environmental conservation and understanding what the needs of the people are who are local to the area so that you can help to improve their quality of life. It also involves learning more about the history of other cities and preserving historical landmarks.

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Many argue that the tourism industry is the largest industry in the world. While its actual value is difficult to accurately determine, the economic potential of the tourism industry is indisputable. In fact, it is because of the positive economic impacts that most destinations embark on their tourism journey.

When we think of the joys that come with the adventures of traveling, we often envision exciting trips to beautiful places fit for a perfect photograph, unique foods you won't find at home and encounters with people who are much different from those we are accustomed to.

Tourism allows us to do more than just learn facts about various locations. It allows us to immerse ourselves into the cultures and lifestyles of others and leaves lasting impressions that aren't likely to be forgotten.

With some experts estimating that ecotourism now represents 11.4% of all consumer spending, these sorts of questions have become more and more common. And, as we continue to see more negative impacts of mass tourism on beloved destinations around the world, the answers to these questions will become increasingly vital. Part of the confusion surrounding sustainable travel is the plethora of names being used for it within the industry.

Ecotourism, a movement that began to take shape back in the 1980s, is the oldest and most commonly used word for it. More recent industry buzzwords include sustainable tourism, green tourism, nature tourism, responsible tourism, ethical tourism, mindful travel, conscious travel, pro-poor tourism, and many others.

The rewards that come with the newness and the satisfying learning experiences of travel are irreplaceable, and these benefits can be enhanced through ecotourism. As an eco-tourist, you travel with more than personal satisfaction in mind. You help the planet and you enable people to lead a more fulfilling life.

Local communities, especially those that do not thrive by industrial means, could benefit greatly from tourists who respect their lands while providing additional funding. In unspoiled regions, we are offered a touring experience that reminds us of nature's enchanting qualities and we are commonly introduced to welcoming residents.

When you meet people as you travel sustainably, mutual understanding allows all parties involved to learn about one another. You are able to tell others where you are from and to show them that you would like to tour the area without disturbing their way of life or disrespecting their values. By showing strangers that you care about their feelings and concerns, they view you as a representative of your home and as an ally. This creates a sense of unity and cultural sensitivity.

We live in a very diverse world full of eclectic people who live off the land and depend on what nature provides. Commercial tourist attractions may be placed in a specific area, but that doesn't mean it gives back to these communities. Instead, large corporations tend to change the way of living for some natives depending on what will be most profitable. When this happens, locals often relocate and are devastated on both a physical and emotional level due to the stresses that come with moving. Many of these indigenous cultures have been deluded, or destroyed altogether, to set up for tourism, but it doesn't have to be that way. Traveling to local attractions offers exciting experiences and the funding you provide to these places is shared amongst the community, contributing to more jobs and a boost in the local economy.

Unfortunately, many of the travel experiences we take part in do not take into consideration how it affects our planet and the well-being of people. There are many popular attractions that are insensitive to the environment and animals. These places continue to make a large amount of money because many people are unaware of the harm and pain it causes, simply viewing it as amusement. On the other hand, lesser-known attractions may not be able to advertise or host a large number of guests at once, but deserve the publicity and funding to help them move forward. When we visit these places and tell others about the experience, we are helping to promote eco-friendly businesses and keep them in operation.

Becoming a more responsible traveler is the best way to ensure your adventures are positive for the local people and the planet. When the core principles of ecotourism are applied, it can stimulate financial growth in developing nations, strengthening the global economy.

Individually, one person taking these baby steps to going green might not seem to make much of an impact. But if we all take simple strides towards being more conscious of our choices, collectively we can make a world of difference.

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